

MODULAR DISTANCE APPROACHES AND THE LEARNING COMPETENCIES OF TLE STUDENTS IN THE NEW NORMAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This experimental study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of modular distance approaches and the learning competencies of TLE students in the new normal education. It sought to describe the problem using the pretest and post test scores of two experimental groups, the questions and learning activity sheets were made by the researcher to determine the learning competencies of the respondents. The respondents were the 60 randomly selected grade 8 students of Camflora National High School, this school year 2020-2021. The first group was the 30 respondents who utilized the activity-based approach, while the second group with 30 respondents were exposed to problem-based approach. Statistically, the following findings indicated the meaningful difference between the two groups utilizing the two approaches. The learning competencies of the respondents exposed in two approaches showed that the respondents got a lowest score in the pretest but in the post test their scores apparently improved. In terms of the significant difference between the pretest scores of respondents using the two approaches, the results found out that there is no significant difference, the hypothesis is accepted. When tested for a significant difference between the post test scores of two approaches, it was found out that, there is no significant difference in terms of knowledge and process. However, performance and understanding scores found it significantly different. Therefore, the null hypothesis is partially accepted. Hence, on the test of significant difference on the pretest and post test scores of respondents utilizing the two approaches all variables are significantly different. The hypothesis is therefore, rejected. The new learning modality could support students' learning in this time of pandemic, the two approaches were both effective. But, to develop students higher-order thinking skills, problem-based approach is more effective than activity-based approach.

Keywords: Modular Distance Approaches, Learning Competencies